
ANUBHUTI –A PLACE FOR LEARNING BY EXPERIENCES IN TRANQUILITY

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Meaning

Anubhuti means learning by experience that journeys through different experiments; involving understanding, acceptance or rejection of the outcome.

Anubhuti is a process of living.

The logo of “Anubhuti” is the emerging Sun which indicates the journey from darkness to light, from darkness to realization - exemplifying the joy of young minds seeking unexplored frontiers of knowledge.

Education is a by-product of practical work. Knowledge and work are one.

Vision :

Anubhuti was instituted in Jalgaon (Maharashtra) to provide quality English medium education to the children of the most deprived and underprivileged part of our society. Anubhuti is a primary day school that is totally free. Besides academic study, it provides the school children free uniforms, books, meals and medical attention to facilitate their learning.

Zeal to establish Anubhuti

Bhavarlal H. Jain is the Founder Chairman of Jain Irrigation Systems Ltd. The company has a creditable history of pioneering and successfully running several internationally acclaimed institutions that have a high social impact.

From its inception, it remains committed to sharing its profits for the greater good of the community. Bhavarlal H. Jain had long felt the need of a world-class residential school for the children of this region. Anubhuti Residential school was started on 07/07/2007 with the idea of providing a sound education for children.

The founder firmly believes that social circumstances should not be a limiting factor in anyone's growth. Out of this belief, and with the support of the Jain family and Jain Irrigation, emerged another school also called Anubhuti. This is exclusively for children of families below the poverty line in Jalgaon.

Working Environment At Anubhuti English Medium School :

The children had absolutely no background of an English medium education. The school has been growing each year as the children progress to a higher class.

Following the ICSE curriculum, Anubhuti integrates education with activities that stimulate the children's imagination and promote exploration through observation. The resultant education enables an all-round development while making the children happy learners.

This School for underprivileged children is providing quality education with facilities comparable to the best schools. The classrooms have furniture and facilities designed for children. Each child is given a little pigeon-hole in which

They keep their personal things like school books, pencils and mat for sitting. The writing desks for the children are made in the shape of arcs and three children share one desk. The idea is to help the children get a sense of responsibility for that which is their individual belonging as well as for those that are community owned. This directly reflects one of the principles of education at Anubhuti, where the limitations of individuality and need for interdependence are emphasized.

An excellent library stocked with children's books and magazines is also provided. Co-curricular activities of music, dance and line arts are a regular part of schooling.

The school provides nutritious food for all. A fruit at eleven, a nourishing meal of vegetables, chapatis and khichdi at lunch and juice and snacks at four in the afternoon. On festivals and special occasions, a sweet dish is also included.

As part of the socially useful production work of the Anubhuti Residential School, the senior students visit Anubhuti to interact with the children. The two groups of children put up entertainment and demos for each other. This integration of children from different social strata in an educational set-up are mutually beneficial - the social and economic ramifications of this would certainly in two years later, as these children grow up..

Criteria For Selection Of Students

The students studying at Anubhuti were selected after conducting a door - to door survey of the Below the Poverty Line cardholders. The survey revealed a huge number of deserving students. Hence, the criteria were further refined to ensure that children from the worst economic and difficult family conditions were given the opportunity to be educated. The type of house in which the family lived (i.e. tin houses or partitioned sheds or cement houses), and the ratio of earning members to the size of the family formed part of the criteria. Girls were given preference, Initially, more students were enrolled as we were expecting some dropouts. Credit goes equally to the staff, organization and the students that the attendance was very good and there was not a single dropout!

For Many of its students, Anubhuti is an island of peace, a real home where they live, eat and paly during the day, while learning in a safe environment.

Teachers at Anubhuti :

While in selecting the teaching staff at Anubhuti, in addition to the person's ability to teach, emphasis was laid on the teacher's preference to teach underprivileged children, infinite patience was required from teachers until the children adjusted to the alien environment, the facilities and the learning methods they had not experienced before. Equally important was their ability to speak fluent Marathi and English, that they were local and had lived or worked in other towns or cities. Spontaneous creativity and ability to adapt to activity- based teaching were favoured. Genuine affection for children ranked among the foremost criteria for selection.

The students call the teachers 'Akka', elder sister. As one 'Akka' explained, even a mother may sometimes scold or be harsh to a child, while an 'Akka' always teaches gently and affectionately. How beautiful is that ! The love and care taken by them probably is very rare in normal schools. The relationship between Teachers and Students is really heart touching, unforgettable and indescribable.

The teachers are also provided with ongoing training in various aspects of creative teaching. As activity- based teaching is the norm here, the teachers work both independently and together to create many role plays skits and projects that drive the lessons home to the Children.

Among the facilities provided to the teachers are computers with access to online research and a well- equipped audio-visual room for showing selected file and animated presentations. Opportunities are provided to the teachers for short-term workshops on activity-based and methods of teaching.

Education at Anubhuti :

The cornerstone of Anubhuti education is that it is grounded in Indian culture. The children learn about the interdependence of mankind and also learn skills that can one day turn them into entrepreneurs.

Children at Anubhuti are very artistic and quick to learn through actions and demonstration rather than only by the book. Reading and verbalizing are taught via poetry and song.

The National Council for Science and Technology Communication (NCSTC) made recommendations to the Government of India

in 1986 to declare 28th February as the National Science Day. This day commemorates the discovery of the Raman Effect, an important discovery made by the Indian physicist Shri Chandrasekhara Venkata Raman for which he was awarded the Nobel Prize in Physics in 1930.

In our School we celebrate this day by exhibiting various experiments and projects the students undertook over the past one year. Along with it we also bring out STEMLET as proof of our continuing commitment of foster scientific temper and popularize science among students.

Summary

Many schools in India are established after Independence. According to our India's vision 2020 there must be 100% Literacy, crossing poverty line and many more. But the Education in India is possible only to those who are capable of paying money. What about those who are marginalized and how can we make them to take active contribution in developing our country? These points made, Shri Bhavarlalji Jain To Start Anubhuti for everyone. Education at Anubhuti is a multi-pronged approach to prepare our children for life. It is believed that Indian culture, tradition and values are what eventually sustain the quality of lives we lead and aim at the holistic growth of everyone involved, in terms of physical, intellectual as well as socio-spiritual levels.